

Synthesis of some New Thienopyrimidines containing 4-Thiazolidinone Moiety

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The reaction of 4-mercaptopyrimidines (1) with halogenated active methylene in aqueous sodium carbonate gave compounds 2. Compound 2c, g were allowed to react with hydrazine hydrate in ethanol to give the acid hydrazides (4a, b). The latter were condensed with aromatic aldehydes and ketones to give the corresponding hydrazones (5). Cyclocondensation of thioglycolic acid on the hydrazones (5) gave the thiazolidinonothienopyrimidines (6).

SEVERAL substituted-4-thiazolidinones have been found to have many physiological activities¹. It was of interest to incorporate these molecules into the well-known pharmaceutical properties of pyrimidine derivatives².

The reaction³ of 4-mercaptopyrimidines (1a, b) with a variety of halogenated methylene compounds in aqueous sodium carbonate gives 4-alkylmercapto- and/or 4-carboxymethylmercaptopyrimidines (2a-h).

The structure of 2c was confirmed by nmr spectrum, δ 3.1 (6H, s, 2-CH₃), 4.1 (2H, CH₂), 1.4 (3H, t, CH₃ of ester) and 4.4 (2H, q, CH₂ of ester).

Compound 2c and/or 2g was dissolved in ethanol, a few drops of triethylamine added, and the reaction mixture refluxed to give the thienopyrimidines (3a, b).

Compounds 3a, b were synthesised by another route by refluxing compound 1a and/or 1b with ethyl bromoacetate in aqueous sodium carbonate. The structure of 3a was confirmed by nmr spectrum, δ 3.1 (3H, s, CH₃), 1.3 (3H, t, CH₃ of ester) and 4.3 (2H, q, CH₂ of ester). Also, 2c, g were allowed to react with hydrazine hydrate⁴ (98%) in ethanolic

solution to give the corresponding acid hydrazides (4a, b).

Moreover, condensation of 4a, b with aromatic aldehydes or ketones in ethanolic solution gave the corresponding hydrazones (5a-o).

On the other hand, cyclocondensation of thioglycolic acid⁵ on the hydrazones (5a, b, d, e, g, i-o) in dry benzene gave the thiazolidinonothienopyrimidine derivatives (6a, b, d, e, g, i-o).

The structure of 6a was confirmed by its elemental and ir spectral data, ν_{max} 3380 (NH), 1670 (C=O of secondary amide) and 1650 cm⁻¹ (C=O of thiazolidinone).

Moreover, the acid hydrazides (4a, b) were reacted with phenylisothiocyanate⁶ to give the pyrimidine-

N-phenylhydrazine carbothioamides (7a, b).

7a, b

Compounds 7a, b were refluxed with chloroacetyl chloride⁷ in methylene chloride to give the thiazolidinothienopyrimidines (8a, b).

8a, b

The structures of 8a, b were established by elemental and ir spectral data, ν_{max} 1 740 (C=O of thiazolidinone), 3 460 (NH of secondary amide) and 1 550 cm^{-1} (C=N), and by independent synthesis by reaction of 7a, b with ethyl bromoacetate or monochloroacetic acid⁸ and anhydrous sodium acetate in ethanol, the product being identical in all respects with that obtained (8a, b) from the above reaction.

On the other hand, a mixture of 7a, phenacyl bromide and anhydrous sodium acetate in ethanol was refluxed for 2 h to give the thiazolidinothienopyrimidines (9).

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The structure of 9 was established from analytical and ir spectral data, ν_{max} 1 640 (C=O of secondary amide), 3 340–3 280 (NH) and 1 580–1 550 cm^{-1} (C=N).

Experimental

All melting points determined are uncorrected. Ir spectra (KBr) were carried out using a Pye-Unicam SP 200G spectrophotometer and nmr spectra using a EM 390 spectrometer.

5-Acetyl-2-aryl-6-methyl-4-mercaptopyrimidine (1a, b): The compounds were prepared according to the reported methods^{15,16}.

5-Acetyl-4-alkylmercapto-2-aryl-6-methylpyrimidines (2a, b, e, f): A mixture of equimolar quantities of 1a, b (0.01 mol), methyl, ethyl or benzyl iodide (0.01 mol) and sodium methoxide (0.01 mol) in methanol (30 ml) was refluxed for 2 h and then cooled. The resulting precipitate was filtered, washed with methanol, dried and recrystallised from petroleum ether (b.p. 60–80°)–benzene mixture to give colourless needle-crystals (Table 1).

5-Acetyl-2-aryl-4-carboxymethylmercapto-6-methylpyrimidines (2d, h): A mixture of 1a, b (0.01 mol) in sodium carbonate solution and monochloroacetic acid (0.01 mol) was warmed for 20 min, then cooled and acidified by dilute HCl. The resulting precipitate was filtered, washed with water, dried and recrystallised from benzene to give colourless needle-crystals (Table 1).

5-Acetyl-2-aryl-4-ethoxycarbonylmethylmercapto-6-methylpyrimidines (2c, g): 1a, b (0.01 mol) was dissolved in aqueous sodium carbonate (20 ml) and ethyl bromoacetate (0.01 mol) was added dropwise while stirring and then stirred for 1 h. The resulting precipitate was filtered, washed with water, dried and recrystallised from ethanol to give colourless crystals (Table 1).

TABLE 1—ANALYTICAL AND PHYSICAL DATA OF COMPOUNDS 2

Compd. no.	Ar	R	M.p. °C	Yield %	Mol. formula	Analysis : Found/(Calcd.)		
						C	H	N
2a	2-Furyl	CH ₃	82–4	70	C ₁₂ H ₁₂ N ₂ O ₂ S	58.40 (58.06)	4.60 (4.83)	11.50 (11.29)
2b	2-Furyl	C ₂ H ₅	78–9	73	C ₁₃ H ₁₄ N ₂ O ₂ S	59.70 (59.50)	6.10 (6.00)	10.70 (10.68)
2c	2-Furyl	CH ₂ CO ₂ C ₂ H ₅	80–1	95	C ₁₅ H ₁₆ N ₂ O ₄ S	56.70 (56.25)	5.20 (5.00)	8.80 (8.78)
2d	2-Furyl	CH ₂ COOH	158–60	83	C ₁₃ H ₁₂ N ₂ O ₄ S	53.40 (53.40)	4.40 (4.10)	9.50 (9.58)
2e	<i>p</i> -OCH ₃ .C ₆ H ₄	CH ₂ .C ₆ H ₄	153–55	43	C ₂₁ H ₂₀ N ₂ O ₂ S	69.00 (69.23)	5.30 (5.49)	7.40 (7.69)
2f	<i>p</i> -OCH ₃ .C ₆ H ₄	C ₂ H ₅	156–57	40	C ₁₈ H ₁₈ N ₂ O ₂ S	63.40 (63.57)	5.90 (5.96)	7.70 (9.27)
2g	<i>p</i> -OCH ₃ .C ₆ H ₄	CH ₂ CO ₂ C ₂ H ₅	92–3	65	C ₁₉ H ₂₀ N ₂ O ₄ S	59.50 (60.00)	5.70 (5.50)	7.70 (7.77)
2h	<i>p</i> -OCH ₃ .C ₆ H ₄	CH ₂ COOH	118–19	86	C ₁₇ H ₁₆ N ₂ O ₄ S	57.70 (57.83)	4.70 (4.81)	8.50 (8.43)

Ethyl-4,5-dimethyl-2-aryl-thieno(2,3-d)pyrimidine-6-carboxylate (3a, b): The compounds were synthesised by two different methods. *Method (A)*: A mixture of 1a, b (0.01 mol) and ethyl bromoacetate (0.01 mol) in aqueous sodium carbonate (20 ml) was refluxed for 30 min and then cooled. The resulting precipitate was filtered, washed with water, dried and recrystallised from ethanol to give colourless crystals.

Method (B): To 2c, g dissolved in ethanol (30 ml) was added a few drops of triethylamine. The reaction mixture was refluxed for 1 h and then cooled. The resulting precipitate was filtered, dried and recrystallised from methanol to give colourless crystals: 3a, m.p. 150–52° (Found: C, 59.40; H, 4.50; N, 9.40. $C_{15}H_{14}N_2O_3S$ calcd. for: C, 59.60; H, 4.63; N, 9.27%); 3b, m.p. 167–68° (Found: C, 62.90; H, 5.40; N, 8.30. $C_{18}H_{18}N_2O_3S$ calcd. for: C, 63.15; H, 5.26; N, 8.18%).

5-Acetyl-2-aryl-4-carboxhydrazide methylmercapto-6-methylpyrimidine (4a, b): A mixture of 2c, g (0.01 mol) and hydrazine hydrate (98%; 0.01 mol) was dissolved in ethanol (30 ml). The solution after shaking was kept at room temperature for 10 min. The resulting precipitate was filtered, washed with ethanol, dried and recrystallised from ethanol to give colourless crystals (4a), m.p. 165–66° (Found: C, 51.20; H, 4.60; N, 18.00. $C_{18}H_{14}N_4O_3S$ calcd. for: C, 50.98; H, 4.54; N, 18.30%); 4b, m.p. 152–53° (Found: C, 55.20; H, 5.00; N, 16.20. $C_{18}H_{18}N_4O_3S$ calcd. for: C, 55.49; H, 5.20; N, 16.18%).

5-Acetyl-2-aryl-4-carboxhydrazone methylmercapto-6-methylpyrimidines (5a–o): A mixture of 4a, b (0.01 mol) and the appropriate aldehyde or ketone (0.01 mol) in methanol (30 ml) was refluxed for 1 h and then concentrated and cooled. The resulting precipitate was filtered, washed with methanol, dried and recrystallised from methanol–DMF mixture to give pale yellow crystals (Table 2).

Thiazolidinethienopyrimidine derivatives (6a, b, d–g, i–o): A mixture of 5a, b, d–g, i–o (0.01 mol) and mercaptoacetic acid (0.01 mol) in dry benzene (30 ml) was refluxed for 20 h. The reaction mixture was then concentrated and cooled, and the resulting precipitate was filtered, dried and recrystallised from toluene to give colourless crystals (Table 3).

5-Acetyl-2-aryl-4-(N-phenylhydrazine carbothioamide)methylmercapto-6-methylpyrimidines (7a, b): A mixture of 4a, b (0.01 mol) and phenyl isothiocyanate (0.01 mol) in dry dioxane (20 ml) was refluxed for 1 h. The reaction mixture was then cooled and the resulting precipitate was filtered, dried and recrystallised from acetone to give gray crystals: (7a), m.p. 205–06° (Found: C, 54.30; H, 4.30; N, 15.80. $C_{20}H_{19}N_5O_3S_2$ calcd. for: C, 54.42; H, 4.30; N, 15.87%); 7b, m.p. 210–11° (Found: C, 57.30; H, 4.60; N, 14.60. $C_{23}H_{23}N_5O_3S_2$ calcd. for: C, 57.38; H, 4.30; N, 14.55%).

2-Aryl-6-(3-phenyl-1,3-thiazolidin-4-one-2-ylidene)-carboxhydrazide-4,5-dimethylthieno[2,3-d]pyrimidines (8a, b): The compounds were synthesised by three different methods. *Method (A)*: 7a, b (0.005 mol) was suspended in methylene chloride (20 ml) and

TABLE 2—ANALYTICAL AND PHYSICAL DATA OF COMPOUNDS 5

Compd. no.	Ar	R ¹	R ²	M.p. °C	Yield %	Mol. formula	Analysis % : Found/(Calcd.)		
							C	H	N
5a	2-Furyl	H	C ₆ H ₄	195–96	82	C ₁₀ H ₁₀ N ₄ O ₇ S	60.20 (60.91)	4.50 (4.56)	14.00 (14.21)
5b	2-Furyl	H	<i>p</i> -OCH ₃ , C ₆ H ₄	173–7	73	C ₂₁ H ₂₀ N ₄ O ₄ S	59.20 (59.43)	4.50 (4.71)	13.00 (13.20)
5c	2-Furyl	H	<i>p</i> -NO ₂ , C ₆ H ₄	185–87	63	C ₂₀ H ₁₇ N ₆ O ₈ S	54.60 (54.66)	3.80 (3.87)	15.50 (15.94)
5d	2-Furyl	H	<i>p</i> -Cl, C ₆ H ₄	187–9	65	C ₂₀ H ₁₇ N ₆ O ₄ SCI	55.80 (56.00)	3.90 (3.96)	13.00 (13.06)
5e	2-Furyl	CH ₃	C ₆ H ₅	155–58	60	C ₂₁ H ₂₀ N ₄ O ₄ S	61.30 (61.76)	5.30 (4.90)	13.50 (13.72)
5f	<i>p</i> -OCH ₃ , C ₆ H ₄	H	C ₆ H ₅	185–86	70	C ₂₂ H ₂₂ N ₄ O ₄ S	63.50 (63.59)	5.30 (5.06)	12.70 (12.90)
5g	<i>p</i> -OCH ₃ , C ₆ H ₄	H	<i>p</i> -OCH ₃ , C ₆ H ₄	193–94	73	C ₂₄ H ₂₄ N ₄ O ₄ S	63.00 (62.06)	5.20 (5.17)	12.30 (12.06)
5h	<i>p</i> -OCH ₃ , C ₆ H ₄	H	<i>p</i> -NO ₂ , C ₆ H ₄	158–60	68	C ₂₃ H ₂₁ N ₆ O ₈ S	57.10 (57.62)	4.30 (4.38)	14.50 (14.61)
5i	<i>p</i> -OCH ₃ , C ₆ H ₄	H	<i>m</i> -NO ₂ , C ₆ H ₄	197–99	78	C ₂₃ H ₂₁ N ₆ O ₈ S	57.40 (57.62)	4.30 (4.38)	14.60 (14.61)
5j	<i>p</i> -OCH ₃ , C ₆ H ₄	H	<i>p</i> -Cl, C ₆ H ₄	194–95	72	C ₂₂ H ₂₁ N ₄ O ₄ SCI	59.10 (58.91)	4.50 (4.48)	11.70 (11.95)
5k	<i>p</i> -OCH ₃ , C ₆ H ₄	H	<i>p</i> -N(CH ₃) ₂ , C ₆ H ₄	215–17	74	C ₂₅ H ₂₇ N ₆ O ₈ S	62.30 (62.89)	5.60 (5.66)	14.50 (14.67)
5l	<i>p</i> -OCH ₃ , C ₆ H ₄	CH ₃	C ₆ H ₅	190–92	65	C ₂₄ H ₂₄ N ₄ O ₇ S	64.10 (64.28)	5.20 (5.32)	12.70 (12.50)
5m	<i>p</i> -OCH ₃ , C ₆ H ₄	CH ₃	<i>p</i> -Cl, C ₆ H ₄	214–16	48	C ₂₄ H ₂₂ N ₄ O ₇ SCI	59.60 (59.68)	4.70 (4.76)	11.80 (11.60)
5n	<i>p</i> -OCH ₃ , C ₆ H ₄	CH ₃	<i>p</i> -Br, C ₆ H ₄	218–19	52	C ₂₄ H ₂₂ N ₄ O ₇ SBr	54.50 (54.64)	4.30 (4.36)	10.50 (10.60)
5o	<i>p</i> -OCH ₃ , C ₆ H ₄	CH ₃	<i>p</i> -CH ₃ , C ₆ H ₄	198–99	44	C ₂₅ H ₂₆ N ₄ O ₇ S	66.20 (66.37)	5.70 (5.75)	12.30 (12.38)

TABLE 3—ANALYTICAL AND PHYSICAL DATA OF COMPOUNDS 6

Compd. no.	Ar	R ¹	R ²	M.p. °C	Yield %	Mol. formula	Analysis % : Found/(Calcd.)		
							C	H	N
6a	2-Furyl	H	C ₆ H ₅	253–55	40	C ₁₁ H ₁₀ N ₄ O ₂ S ₂	58.70 (58.66)	4.30 (4.00)	12.40 (12.44)
6b	2-Furyl	H	<i>p</i> -OCH ₃ .C ₆ H ₄	245–46	42	C ₁₂ H ₁₀ N ₄ O ₄ S ₂	57.60 (57.50)	4.20 (4.16)	11.50 (11.66)
6d	2-Furyl	H	<i>p</i> -Cl.C ₆ H ₄	254–55	45	C ₁₁ H ₁₇ N ₄ O ₄ S ₂ Cl	53.90 (54.49)	3.30 (3.51)	11.70 (11.56)
6e	2-Furyl	CH ₃	C ₆ H ₅	198–99	22	C ₁₁ H ₁₀ N ₄ O ₂ S ₂	59.60 (59.48)	4.40 (4.31)	12.30 (12.07)
6g	<i>p</i> -OCH ₃ .C ₆ H ₄	H	<i>p</i> -OCH ₃ .C ₆ H ₄	163–65	43	C ₁₂ H ₁₄ N ₄ O ₄ S ₂	59.70 (60.00)	4.70 (4.62)	10.80 (10.77)
6i	<i>p</i> -OCH ₃ .C ₆ H ₄	H	<i>m</i> -NO ₂ .C ₆ H ₄	220–22	32	C ₁₁ H ₁₁ N ₅ O ₂ S ₂	56.30 (56.07)	4.00 (3.92)	13.40 (13.08)
6j	<i>p</i> -OCH ₃ .C ₆ H ₄	H	<i>p</i> -Cl.C ₆ H ₄	150–53	32	C ₁₁ H ₁₁ N ₄ O ₂ S ₂ Cl	55.30 (55.14)	4.10 (4.20)	11.60 (11.19)
6k	<i>p</i> -OCH ₃ .C ₆ H ₄	H	<i>p</i> -N(CH ₃) ₂ .C ₆ H ₄	230–31	30	C ₁₇ H ₁₇ H ₂ O ₂ S ₂	60.20 (60.79)	5.20 (5.07)	13.30 (13.13)
6l	<i>p</i> -OCH ₃ .C ₆ H ₄	CH ₃	C ₆ H ₅	200–02	40	C ₁₀ H ₁₄ N ₄ O ₂ N ₂	62.00 (61.90)	4.70 (4.76)	11.20 (11.11)
6m	<i>p</i> -OCH ₃ .C ₆ H ₄	CH ₃	<i>p</i> -Cl.C ₆ H ₄	193–95	32	C ₁₀ H ₁₁ N ₄ O ₂ S ₂ Cl	57.70 (57.94)	4.30 (4.27)	10.50 (10.40)
6n	<i>p</i> -OCH ₃ .C ₆ H ₄	CH ₃	<i>p</i> -Br.C ₆ H ₄	216–17	41	C ₁₀ H ₁₁ N ₄ O ₂ S ₂ Br	53.40 (53.52)	3.80 (3.95)	9.50 (9.61)
6o	<i>p</i> -OCH ₃ .C ₆ H ₄	CH ₃	<i>p</i> -CH ₃ .C ₆ H ₄	225–26	37	C ₁₇ H ₁₆ N ₄ O ₂ S ₂	62.30 (62.55)	4.90 (5.02)	10.70 (10.81)

refluxed with chloroacetyl chloride (0.01 mol) for 10 h. The reaction mixture was then cooled and the resulting precipitated was filtered, dried and recrystallised from petroleum ether (b.p. 40–60°) – benzene mixture to give colourless crystals.

Method (B): A mixture of 7a, b (0.01 mol), anhydrous sodium acetate (0.05 mol) and ethyl bromoacetate (0.01 mol) in absolute ethanol (30 ml) was refluxed for 3 h. The reaction mixture was cooled, diluted with water and allowed to stand at room temperature for 2 h. The resulting precipitate was filtered, washed with water, dried and crystallised from petroleum ether (b.p. 40–60°) – benzene mixture to give colourless crystals.

Method (C): A mixture of 7a, b (0.01 mol), anhydrous sodium acetate (0.05 mol) and monochloroacetic acid in glacial acetic acid (30 ml) was refluxed for 5 h. The reaction mixture was poured on ice–water and kept in refrigerator for 24 h. The resulting precipitate was filtered, washed with water, dried and crystallised from petroleum ether (b.p. 40–60°) – benzene mixture to give colourless crystals (8a), m.p. 100–02° (Found : C, 54.80 ; H, 4.00 ; N, 14.55. C₁₂H₁₂N₄O₄S₂ calcd. for : C, 54.88 ; H, 3.95 ; N, 14.55%) ; 8b, m.p. 95–6° (Found : C, 57.60 ; H, 4.50 ; N, 13.60. C₁₂H₁₂N₄O₄S₂ calcd. for : C, 57.60 ; H, 4.41 ; N, 13.43%).

2-Furyl-6-(3,5-dimethyl-1,3-thiazolidin-2-ylidene-4-ene)carboxhydrazide-4,5-dimethylthieno[2,3-d]pyrimidines (9): A mixture of 7a (0.01 mol), anhydrous sodium acetate (0.05 mol) and phenacyl bromide (0.01 mol) in absolute ethanol (30 ml) was refluxed for 2 h. The reaction mixture was poured in ice–water. The resulting precipitate was filtered off,

dried and crystallised from petroleum ether (b.p. 100–20°) – benzene mixture to give green crystals (9), m.p. 110–12° (Found : C, 64.30 ; H, 4.00 ; N, 13.20. C₂₆H₂₁N₅O₂S₂ calcd. for : C, 64.24 ; H, 4.01 ; N, 13.38%).

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